
A CTC-ALIGNED LIGHTWEIGHT KOREAN TTS PIPELINE WITHOUT EXTERNAL ALIGNERS

PREPRINT

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April 14, 2026

ABSTRACT

Lightweight text-to-speech (TTS) models have gained attention for their fast inference and low resource requirements, but they typically depend on external aligners such as the Montreal Forced Aligner (MFA) during training. For Korean, the publicly available MFA acoustic models and pronunciation dictionaries are of limited quality, requiring substantial manual effort to set up a reliable alignment pipeline. In this paper, we propose a lightweight Korean TTS pipeline that can be trained without any external aligner. The proposed method introduces a Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) aligner that classifies mel-spectrogram frames directly into phonemes and extracts phoneme durations via forced alignment. Training is organized into two stages: in Stage 1, the CTC aligner is jointly trained with the acoustic model to obtain alignments; in Stage 2, the acoustic model is retrained from scratch using the fixed alignment targets extracted by the Stage 1 aligner. While the monotonic alignment search (MAS) used by larger models fails to converge in lightweight configurations because the encoder representation lacks sufficient capacity, CTC alignment operates directly on the mel spectrogram and is therefore robust to the encoder’s capacity. For vocoding, we use a lightweight HiFi-GAN fine-tuned on Korean speech data. On the KSS dataset, the proposed method achieves a MOS of 3.67 without any external aligner, outperforming an MFA-based counterpart (3.46) at the same model scale.

Keywords text-to-speech · lightweight model · Korean · CTC alignment · forced alignment

1 Introduction

Recent deep-learning-based text-to-speech (TTS) systems have reached a quality level at which the synthesized speech is perceptually close to natural recordings. However, most high-quality TTS models rely on millions of parameters, which makes them difficult to deploy on edge devices or in real-time applications. To address this limitation, lightweight TTS models such as EfficientSpeech [1] have been proposed. These models still depend on an external aligner, typically the Montreal Forced Aligner (MFA) [2], to extract phoneme-to-frame alignments prior to training.

MFA works well for major languages such as English, but for Korean the publicly available acoustic models and pronunciation dictionaries are of limited quality, resulting in lower alignment accuracy and requiring substantial manual effort to build reliable lexicons and acoustic models. This limits the reproducibility and practical deployability of lightweight Korean TTS.

Large models such as Glow-TTS [3] and VITS [4] avoid external aligners by using online Monotonic Alignment Search (MAS). When MAS is applied directly to a lightweight configuration with a reduced feature dimension, however, the encoder does not have enough representational capacity, and the alignment fails to converge. Since MAS relies on the similarity between encoder outputs and mel-spectrogram representations, the alignment quality degrades as the encoder’s feature dimension shrinks.

In this paper, we propose a two-stage training pipeline that uses a Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) [5] aligner to address these issues. The CTC aligner is an independent lightweight module that classifies mel-spectrogram frames directly into phonemes, so its alignment quality is decoupled from the encoder’s representational capacity. In Stage 1, the CTC aligner is jointly trained with the acoustic model to obtain alignments; in Stage 2, the acoustic model is retrained from scratch using fixed alignment targets, which removes the moving-target problem caused by online alignment. This enables a lightweight Korean TTS model to be trained without any external alignment tool. For vocoding, we use a lightweight HiFi-GAN [6] fine-tuned on Korean speech data, keeping the overall pipeline compact.

2 Related Work

FastSpeech 2 [7] is a non-autoregressive TTS model that predicts phoneme durations, pitch, and energy explicitly, achieving fast synthesis. However, it requires alignment information extracted by MFA during training.

Glow-TTS [3] and **VITS** [4] introduced online MAS to train TTS models without external aligners. MAS uses dynamic programming to search for a monotonic alignment path based on the similarity between encoder outputs and the mel spectrogram. Although this approach works well for models with tens of millions of parameters, it can fail to converge in lightweight configurations because the encoder does not provide sufficiently discriminative representations.

CTC-based alignment. CTC [5] was originally proposed for sequence labelling tasks in speech recognition in which the alignment between input and output is unknown. More recently, RAD-TTS [8] and related work have adopted CTC for TTS alignment. A CTC aligner classifies mel frames directly into phonemes and therefore operates independently of the encoder’s representational capacity.

HiFi-GAN [6] is a GAN-based vocoder that uses a Multi-Period Discriminator and a Multi-Scale Discriminator and synthesizes high-fidelity waveforms even in lightweight configurations.

Figure 1: Proposed pipeline. The dashed region indicates the CTC alignment path that is used only in Stage 1; in Stage 2, the acoustic model is trained with fixed targets extracted by the Stage 1 aligner.

3 Proposed Method

The proposed pipeline trains a lightweight TTS model without any external aligner through a two-stage procedure based on CTC alignment. Fig. 1 shows the overall pipeline.

3.1 Model Architecture

The base model follows the architecture of EfficientSpeech [1]. The phoneme encoder is composed of hierarchical attention blocks that fuse multi-scale features to produce phoneme representations. Duration, pitch, and energy predictors then predict phoneme-level acoustic features, which are expanded to the frame level by a length regulator; a mel decoder subsequently generates an 80-channel mel spectrogram. The final waveform is synthesized by a lightweight HiFi-GAN [6] vocoder fine-tuned on Korean speech data. In the Base configuration, the acoustic model has approximately 3.9 M parameters.

3.2 CTC Aligner

The root cause of MAS failure in lightweight models is that MAS relies on the similarity between encoder outputs and mel-spectrogram features. When the encoder’s feature dimension is small, the similarity is not discriminative enough to produce a stable alignment.

To address this, we introduce a CTC aligner that classifies mel-spectrogram frames directly into phonemes. The aligner is a lightweight module that operates independently of the encoder and consists of two one-dimensional convolutional layers with GELU activations and a linear output layer:

$$\mathbf{z}_t = \text{Linear}(\text{GELU}(\text{Conv}_2(\text{GELU}(\text{Conv}_1(\mathbf{x}_t)))))) \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{V}|+1}, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x}_t is the t -th mel frame, $|\mathcal{V}|$ is the size of the phoneme set, and $+1$ accounts for the CTC blank token. The CTC aligner has approximately 0.45 M parameters, which adds negligible overhead to the overall pipeline.

3.3 Two-Stage Training

Stage 1: Joint training with CTC. The CTC aligner is trained jointly with the acoustic model. The CTC loss [5] is applied to the aligner’s output:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{ctc}} = -\log p(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{x}), \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{y} is the phoneme sequence and \mathbf{x} is the mel spectrogram. The CTC loss marginalizes over all possible alignment paths, so explicit frame-level alignment labels are not required. During this stage, phoneme durations are obtained online via CTC forced alignment, and frame-level pitch and energy are aggregated to the phoneme level as

$$\bar{f}_{0,n} = \frac{\sum_t A_{n,t} \cdot f_{0,t}}{\sum_t A_{n,t}}, \quad \bar{e}_n = \frac{\sum_t A_{n,t} \cdot e_t}{\sum_t A_{n,t}}, \quad (3)$$

where $A_{n,t}$ is a binary path matrix constructed from the forced alignment. Alignment is extracted with a Viterbi-based CTC forced aligner, implemented efficiently using the C++ routines provided by torchaudio.

Stage 2: Retraining with fixed targets. Once the CTC aligner from Stage 1 has converged, we run it once over the entire training set to extract fixed duration, pitch, and energy targets. The CTC aligner is then discarded, and the acoustic model is retrained from scratch with the fixed targets.

This separation into two stages is motivated by a moving-target problem in Stage 1: because the CTC aligner produces slightly different alignments for every batch, the duration and pitch targets are non-stationary. We observe that the duration loss oscillates during Stage 1 training and that the pitch predictor becomes unstable as a result, which we attribute to the limited capacity of the lightweight model, making it difficult to adapt to continuously shifting targets. Switching to fixed targets gives the predictors a consistent supervision signal and leads to stable convergence (see Fig. 2 and Table 2).

3.4 Loss Functions

The Stage 1 training objective is

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{stage1}} = 10\mathcal{L}_{\text{mel}} + 2\mathcal{L}_{\text{pitch}} + 2\mathcal{L}_{\text{energy}} + 4\mathcal{L}_{\text{dur}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{ctc}}. \quad (4)$$

In Stage 2 the CTC loss is removed and only the acoustic losses remain:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{stage2}} = 10\mathcal{L}_{\text{mel}} + 2\mathcal{L}_{\text{pitch}} + 2\mathcal{L}_{\text{energy}} + 4\mathcal{L}_{\text{dur}}. \quad (5)$$

\mathcal{L}_{mel} is an L1 loss, $\mathcal{L}_{\text{pitch}}$ and $\mathcal{L}_{\text{energy}}$ are MSE losses, and \mathcal{L}_{dur} is an MSE loss in the log domain.

3.5 Advantages of CTC Alignment over MAS

MAS determines the alignment from the similarity between the encoder output $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d}$ and the mel representation $\mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times d}$. When the feature dimension d is small, this similarity becomes less discriminative. In preliminary experiments on EfficientSpeech Base ($d=128$), MAS failed to form a diagonal alignment, and the prosody and durations of the synthesized speech were severely distorted. In contrast, the CTC aligner takes the 80-dimensional mel spectrogram as direct input and classifies phonemes, so its behaviour is decoupled from the encoder’s dimensionality. This yields a more robust alignment for lightweight models.

In addition, MAS-based approaches couple alignment extraction and model training, which introduces a moving-target problem. Our two-stage separation explicitly avoids this issue.

4 Experiments

4.1 Experimental Setup

Dataset. We use the Korean single-speaker open-source dataset KSS [9] (approximately 12 hours, 12,854 utterances). Audio is resampled to 22,050 Hz, and 80-channel mel spectrograms are extracted (FFT size 1024, hop length 256, window length 1024). Pitch is computed with the DIO algorithm of the WORLD vocoder, and energy is the L2 norm of each STFT frame. Korean text is converted to a jamo-level phoneme sequence after G2P conversion.

Model configuration. We use the EfficientSpeech Base configuration (encoder depth 2, embedding dimension 128, reduction ratio 1, 2 attention heads, 3 decoder blocks each of depth 3, MixFFN expansion ratio 2), giving an acoustic model with approximately 3.9 M parameters. The CTC aligner has approximately 0.45 M parameters. The vocoder is HiFi-GAN V2 [6] (925 K parameters), fine-tuned on a mixture of KSS and a subset of the AI Hub multi-speaker conversational TTS corpus [10] (approximately 38 hours in total). We use AdamW with a learning rate of 5×10^{-4} and a cosine annealing scheduler. Stage 1 (joint CTC training) is run for 1,500 epochs and Stage 2 (fixed-target retraining) for 3,000 epochs.

Figure 2: Training loss curves. (Left) In Stage 1 the CTC loss oscillates, reflecting the moving-target behaviour of online alignment. (Right) In Stage 2 all losses converge stably with fixed alignment targets.

Evaluation. We use the Mean Opinion Score (MOS) for subjective evaluation. Ten Korean native speakers rated the naturalness of the synthesized samples on a 1 (very poor) to 5 (very good) scale.

4.2 Results

Table 1 compares our model with prior TTS systems. The †-marked entries report MOS on LJSpeech (English) as published in the original papers, so a direct numerical comparison is limited; nevertheless, the table makes the differences in model scale and alignment strategy explicit. EfficientSpeech [1] reported CMOS rather than absolute MOS, achieving comparable quality to FastSpeech 2 (-0.14 CMOS). On KSS, our MFA-based model achieves a stable MOS of 3.46 but depends on an external aligner. Our MAS-based model fails to synthesize intelligible speech because the alignment does not converge with the lightweight encoder ($d=128$). The proposed CTC-based pipeline achieves a

Table 1: Synthesis quality comparison on KSS. † MOS values are taken from the original papers on LJSpeech (English); direct comparison is therefore limited. ‡ Adds 0.45 M CTC aligner parameters only during training. * MAS alignment failed to converge with the lightweight encoder ($d=128$), so no intelligible synthesis was produced.

Method	Align.	Params	MOS †
FastSpeech 2 [7]†	MFA	27 M	3.83
Glow-TTS [3]†	MAS	29 M	4.01
VITS [4]†	MAS	37 M	4.43
EfficientSpeech [1]†	MFA	0.3–3.9 M	–
Ours + MFA	MFA	3.9 M	3.46
Ours + MAS	MAS	3.9 M	–*
Ours + CTC (proposed)	CTC	3.9 M‡	3.67

MOS of 3.67 with only 3.9 M parameters and without any external aligner, outperforming the MFA-based counterpart by 0.21 points.

4.3 Convergence Analysis

Fig. 2 shows the training-loss curves for both stages. The CTC loss decreases rapidly in Stage 1, indicating that the aligner converges early. However, online alignment yields slightly different paths from batch to batch, which destabilizes duration and pitch prediction (Fig. 2, left). Switching to fixed targets in Stage 2 leads to stable convergence of all loss terms (Fig. 2, right). Table 2 compares the final losses between the two stages: after switching to fixed targets, the pitch loss decreases by 39.4%, the energy loss by 37.5%, and the duration loss by 22.7%, confirming the benefit of the fixed-target stage.

Table 2: Final losses for Stage 1 and Stage 2.

Loss	Stage 1 (ep 1500)	Stage 2 (ep 3000)
Mel	0.407	0.373
Duration	0.022	0.017
Pitch	0.033	0.020
Energy	0.024	0.015
CTC	0.031	–

5 Conclusion

We presented a lightweight Korean TTS pipeline that can be trained without any external aligner. We analyzed why MAS becomes unstable in lightweight configurations with reduced feature dimensions and addressed the issue with a two-stage training procedure based on CTC alignment.

In Stage 1 a CTC aligner is jointly trained with the acoustic model to obtain alignments, and in Stage 2 the acoustic model is retrained on fixed targets extracted by the Stage 1 aligner, eliminating the moving-target problem. Because the CTC aligner classifies phonemes directly from the mel spectrogram, alignment quality is decoupled from the encoder’s representational capacity. On KSS, the proposed method achieves a MOS of 3.67, outperforming an MFA-based counterpart (3.46) by 0.21 points at the same model scale. The approach is expected to generalize to other languages for which building an external aligner is difficult, by replacing only the language-specific G2P and text cleaner.

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